

On the Adoption of Continuous-Variable QKD in Optical Networks

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ABSTRACT

Continuous variable quantum key distribution (CV-QKD) is arising as an attractive technology for quantum secure communications in future optical networks, thanks to its higher compatibility with conventional telecommunication systems. In fact, CV-QKD adopts opto-electronic devices of coherent optical systems, enabling the use of commercial off-the-shelf components (COTS) and photonic integrated circuits (PICs). This favors a faster and sustainable adoption of this technology in optical networks. Also, smoother integration within the network infrastructure can be envisioned, in coexistence with classical communications, further facilitated and accelerated by software defined networking (SDN). In this invited contribution, the adoption of CV-QKD in future optical networks is discussed, presenting our recent results.

Keywords: Quantum key distribution (QKD), continuous variable QKD (CV-QKD), optical networks, secure communications, quantum-classical coexistence, software defined networking (SDN).

1. INTRODUCTION

To enable a sustainable and smooth transition towards quantum-secure communications, ensuring optimal resource usage in future optical networks, the introduction of quantum key distribution (QKD) should be carefully studied and continuous advances must be performed at the pace of the technological evolution.

Private communication on QKD protocols is granted by the laws of quantum mechanics that permit to detect the action of an eavesdropper by monitoring its effects on the transmitted information. Alternative QKD systems and protocols have been studied and proposed including discrete variable (DV) and continuous variable (CV) QKD, depending on the nature of the information carrier. Particularly, CV-QKD protocols are based on the modulation and transmission of coherent states (CS) through a quantum channel, often on a fiber link but also through free-space. The distillation of the cryptographic key relies on interpreting the information carried by the transmitted symbols. Despite DV-QKD is more tolerant to channel losses, supporting longer reach, with respect to the CV-QKD, the latter can provide improved performance in terms of secure key rate and it is more compatible with optical communication systems. This directly impacts on i) easier implementation adopting optical coherent technology, instead of requiring single photon detectors as in DV-QKD; ii) increased robustness when the quantum channel is co-propagated with classical optical channels.

A key point often debated on CV-QKD is the security assessment. Accordingly, in this work (on Sec. 2), we provide a short discussion related to this aspect, expanding what presented in [1], considering practical implementation. We also comment on the adoption of discrete modulation (DM) formats, which would further ease the implementation of CV-QKD adopting similar transmitters as for optical communication systems without the need of implementing Gaussian modulation (GM).

In our previous work [2], we reported on the coexistence of QKD with classical optical systems, based on relevant references, also considering the adoption of specialty fibers. Further advances and remarkable results have been recently achieved on both DV-QKD [3] and CV-QKD [4].

In this work, within Sec. 3, we report our recent results on coexistence analysis, providing further discussion on alternative allocation strategies and considering the advantageous capability of CV-QKD to arbitrarily tuning the operating wavelength. The relevance of the software defined networking (SDN) support towards adopting QKD technology in future optical networks and enabling dynamic QKD networks is discussed in Sec. 4. Finally in Sec. 5, the conclusions on the adoption of CV-QKD in future optical networks are drawn.

2. SECURITY ASSESSMENT OF CV-QKD PROTOCOLS

QKD protocols are restricted to different security levels depending on the possible actions that the eavesdropper can take, allowing to trust or not the noise or losses. Generally, it is reasonable to assume that the security attacks correspond exclusively to actions on the quantum channel, hence the noise and receiver can be trusted [5].

The security of the protocol is associated to the number of bits per symbol that contributes to the secret key. This ratio, known as secret fraction (r), is given by the difference between the information shared by two communication parties (Alice and Bob), and the amount of information that an eavesdropper (Eve) could have access to. The former is a classical quantity generally determined by the Shannon mutual information between the transmitted (Alice's) and received (Bob's) data (I_{AB}), and the latter requires a more general measure of the

quantum mutual information (S_{BE}), which is in general difficult to compute. Assuming attacks to each transmitted symbol measured collectively, the quantum mutual information can be upper bounded (Holevo information), and the bound can be asymptotically attained in the limit of infinitely many symbols. Hence, the secret fraction can be expressed according to the Devetak-Winter formula: $r \geq \beta I_{AB} - S_{BE}$, where β is the reconciliation efficiency of the error correcting code [6]. Usually reverse reconciliation, performed by Alice based on Bob's information on his measurements, is considered to avoid the 3dB loss in case of forward reconciliation.

Proving security against collective attacks is sufficient for GMCS CV-QKD due to optimality of Gaussian attacks, and the key rate converges to the asymptotic one for a large number of symbols (N).

2.1 The finite-size regime

Although the asymptotic bound is useful to define the limitations of the QKD systems and protocols, realistically the protocol employs finite-size blocks of symbols for key generation. In these terms, the secret fraction becomes the ratio between the secret key length divided by the block size. Since the latter is a finite number (N), the eavesdropper cannot have access to the maximal amount of information as the asymptotic bound assumes and the upper bound is not attained, hence the quantum mutual information must be computed differently. In [7], we have compared the results obtained considering both the asymptotic and finite-size formalisms, to determine the required value of N . Specifically, for the analysed case of CV-QKD, we studied the performance in terms of r as a function of the transmission length, using VPIphotonics [8]. We demonstrated that values of N higher than 10^{10} allow to approximate the asymptotic regime and the CV-QKD system can generate secret keys up to 25 km. Using lower values of N , to reduce the complexity of the post-processing phase, is at the expenses of the performance: for example, lowering the value by an order of magnitude ($N=10^9$), the distance decreases to 19 km, while for $N=10^8$, the supported distance (~8 km) is reduced approximately by a factor of 3 with respect to the achievable length in the asymptotic regime. Furthermore, following the quantum state distribution and measurement, the key distillation process consists of digital signal processing (DSP) steps ensuring the correctness, robustness, and secrecy of the protocol, up to their respective failure probabilities. The success rate of these steps is reflected on the length of the secret key, and their effects can be quantified by means of their failure probabilities leading to a composable security analysis of the secret fraction [9].

A complete security analysis of a CV-QKD protocol must then account for the finite total number of symbols used as well as for correctness, robustness and secrecy, in a composable manner. By knowing the characteristics of the QKD system, and the parameters characterizing it, the expected secret fraction can be estimated, depending on the transmittance and excess noise of the quantum channel, that can be rigorously modelled [10].

2.2 Gaussian modulation and discrete modulations

For GMCS, the bound of Holevo information is directly determined by the modulation variance V_{mod} , the channel transmittance $T=T_{\text{ch}} \cdot \eta_{\text{det}} \cdot \eta_{\text{coup}}$, and the excess noise ξ . The excess noise accounts for all different noise sources, including the intrinsic noise ξ_0 of the CV-QKD system and the noise ξ_{NLI} , due to the fiber nonlinearities, and can be expressed as $\xi=\xi_0+\xi_{\text{NLI}}$. The security assessment of GMCS CV-QKD relies on the Gaussianity of either the quantum channel or the coherent state modulation. Protocols featuring both Gaussian assumptions are hence secure, however, limited in range due to the decrease in the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). This can be overcome by adopting DM formats subject to a Gaussian quantum channel. The security of DM protocols is restricted to values of the modulation variance within a limited operation domain in which the protocol is close to indistinguishable from one based on GMCS [6].

Actually, DM protocols can outperform Gaussian modulation in case of high losses and are particularly attractive for their simpler implementation and higher compatibility with fiber optic communication equipment.

3. INTEGRATION OF QKD IN OPTICAL NETWORKS

The integration of QKD technology in optical networks, considering the deployed network infrastructure, is a crucial aspect to take into account for enabling quantum secure communications. This could be especially challenging if the coexistence of quantum and classical channels is required over the same fiber medium, for example when the number of available fibers is limited or for specific network scenarios, segments or applications. To enable the coexistence of amplified classical channels with the quantum channel, an appropriate selection of parameters, such as the channel spacing and the power values should be carefully performed, while appropriately considering and analysing the impairments that can severely affect the co-propagation, such as the channel losses and non-linear effects, as the detrimental spontaneous Raman scattering (SpRS) [2] [7]. It is important to note that CV-QKD systems can be implemented with optical coherent technology components, even COTS, and adopting PICs, providing solutions with reduced cost, power consumption and footprint. Therefore, CV-QKD is appearing as an attractive option for integrating QKD technology within optical networks.

3.1 Quantum channel allocation strategies

The quantum channel allocation is a crucial aspect to carefully address in a coexistence scenario, in order to perform an optimal usage of the network resources, while keeping both the quantum and classical transmission correctly operating. Alternative strategies can be adopted either considering different bands or with a suitable allocation within the C-band adopting wavelength division multiplexing (WDM), as shown in Fig. 1.

In case of DV-QKD, due to the high impact of classical channels co-propagation on the quantum channel performance, the allocation in the O-band has been usually recommended. In this scenario, as shown in Fig. 1(b), the classical channels generated by advanced sliceable bandwidth/bitrate variable transceivers (S-BVTs) would occupy the other bands (e.g., S, C and L), to support the high-capacity traffic demand of future optical networks [11]. Nevertheless, the coexistence of DV-QKD and classical channels in the C-band is also explored and a recent work demonstrated that DV-QKD can coexist in the same C-band with 8 classical channels at 200G with a relative low guard-band of 200GHz [3]. CV-QKD is more robust to the coexistence with classical channels in the same band and it has been recently demonstrated the co-propagation of channels covering the entire C-band requiring 1nm of guard-band [4].

A relevant aspect to take into consideration when adopting a CV-QKD is that by using a tunable laser source, the operating wavelength can be arbitrarily tuned over the spectrum to select the most appropriate channel. On this respect, we have recently demonstrated in [12], that a commercial CV-QKD system can be suitably tuned within the C-band, allowing the system to be configured to operate at any channel of the ITU-T grid. Specifically, the narrow-linewidth laser wavelength at the CV-QKD transmitter has been changed every hour, in steps of 200 GHz, from 193.5 to 195.3 THz, with a reconfiguration time of 7 minutes. Successful performance has been shown achieving secret key rate with mean value of 15.2 kb/s (finite size regime), for 10-hour measurements over a 3.76 dB losses channel (roughly equivalent to 19 km of SMF fiber) [12]. This is a powerful tool, particularly in a coexistence scenario when the quantum channel can be allocated according to the active traffic and to limit the impairments due to the co-propagation with classical channels. Thus, we have investigated the suitable guard-band to be selected for enabling quantum-classical channels coexistence in presence of 8 classical channels at 200Gb/s, spaced by 100GHz according to the ITU-T grid [1]. The spectral allocation of quantum and classical channels is indicated in the inset of Fig 1(a) (case on the top) corresponding to the allocation strategy of Fig 1(c). We have considered a power per channel of 0dBm (total power of 9dBm) to correctly recover the classical channels, while analysing a challenging scenario for the quantum channel, observing that a minimum channel spacing $>100\text{GHz}$ (specifically of 135GHz) is required [1]. We have also investigated the suitable allocation for the quantum channel considering 100GHz spacing with lower power per classical channel, still ensuring correct reception, as well as positive key rate generation [7], by varying the quantum channel spectral position (the bottom of the inset of Fig. 1(a) shows an example). Alternative strategies also considering allocating the quantum channel at the edge of the C-band (Fig. 1(d)-(e)) can be envisioned. Accordingly, a careful study of the impact of the nonlinearities and their possible limitation is required for a suitable channel allocation, as detailed in [13]. Further investigation in this direction is ongoing, also considering more challenging scenarios. This allows properly selecting the quantum channel wavelength and spacing, as well as the power and number of active classical channels, for enabling coexistence and integration of QKD within the deployed network infrastructure, with the support of SDN, as discussed in the next section.

Figure 1. (a) SDN-enabled QKD coexisting with classical optical transmission adopting programmable S-BVT; in the inset of (a) and in (b)-(e), alternative quantum channel allocation strategies.

4. QKD NETWORK ARCHITECTURE EVOLUTION AND SDN

According to previous section results and analysis, it is of particular interest to enable the (re)-configuration of CV-QKD systems by means of SDN. This would not only accelerate the adoption of this technology in future networks, but also enable more dynamic QKD networks in a joint orchestration with classical optical networks, for a suitable channel allocation and optimal network resource usage, as shown in Fig. 1(a). We have identified the relevant programmable parameters, including the QKD system operating wavelength, and suitable interfaces, such as ETSI GS QKD 004, 014, for the key management system (KMS) and the ETSI GS QKD 015 for the configuration and monitoring of the SDN-QKD (SD-QKD) node [1], [12]. We are working on the development of the SD-QKD controller extending the open-source cloud-native ETSI TeraFlow SDN (TFS) controller. The SDN orchestrator coordinates the actions of both the SD-QKD network controller and SD-optical network controller to operate on the QKD node modules, taking into account also the optical networks, as shown in Fig. 1(a), depending on the traffic and channel conditions. This allows moving from a static point-to-point scenario for QKD networks, towards a more dynamic and interoperable paradigm, in coexistence with optical networks.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The adoption in optical networks of CV-QKD is advantageous thanks to the compatibility with optical coherent technology, and the possible implementation with COTS and PICs. Proving security against collective attacks is sufficient for GMCS CV-QKD, with asymptotic convergence for large N . Practical implementations employ finite N , and this should be considered for retrieving the effective key rate and evaluating the performance of the actual CV-QKD system. DM can further improve the compatibility and easiness of implementation, as well as the achievable performance, within a certain operative range for proven security. CV-QKD is more robust in presence of classical channels in the same band. Suitable spectral allocation of the quantum channel should be carefully performed considering several parameters including wavelength tuneability, channel spacing, number and power of classical channels, SpRS and other fiber nonlinearities. For optimal network resource usage, enabling correct transmission of high-capacity optical channels and operation of CV-QKD, SDN is a crucial element, capable to accelerate the adoption of this technology in optical networks and enabling interoperability.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Work partially supported by Horizon Europe ALLEGRO project (101092766), 6G-OPENSEC-KEYS (TSI-063000-2021-61) funded by “Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital” and the European Union-NextGenerationEU in the frameworks of the “Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia” and of the “Mecanismo de Recuperación y Resiliencia” and RELAMPAGO project (Grant PID2021-127916OB-I00), funded by MICIU/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU.

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